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Optimisation of Cowpeas (*Vigna unguiculata*) Inclusion Level in *Chinchilla gigantea* Rabbit Weaner Diets for Enhanced Performance

Author' s Details:

Makiwa Peter¹, Shumba Trust¹, Hore Gladys Muzora¹, Mabhena Wellington Masuku¹, Makiwa Priscilla¹, Makumbe Milton Tinashe¹ and Gadzirayi Christopher T²

¹Henderson Research Institute, P. Bag 2004, Mazowe, Zimbabwe

²BIO-HUB Trust, 6 Lanark Road, Belgravia, Harare

Corresponding Authors: makiwapeter@yahoo.com

gadziravichris@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study sought to determine feed intake, feed conversion ratio (FCR), growth performance of *Chinchilla gigantea* rabbit weaners fed on Cowpeas-Based Diets and the subsequent economics of partially substituting soya beans with cowpeas as protein source. Thirty-six weaner rabbits (eighteen females and eighteen males) were used in a Completely Randomised Block Design where sex was the blocking factor. The diets comprised of 0% cowpeas (control), 25% cowpeas and 30% cowpeas. Average daily feed intake and feed conversion ratio were not significant across the three treatment diets ($p > 0.05$). Average daily weight gains and percentage weight gains were significantly lower for diet three ($p < 0.05$). Average daily weight gains were 13.91g, 11.89g and 11.22g for diet one, two and three respectively. Percentage weight gains were 142.4, 120.2 and 113.4 for diets one, two and three respectively. Average cost per kilogram weight gain was not significant across the three diets ($p > 0.05$). Initial weights had effects on percentage weight gains ($P < 0.05$). Gross margin analysis showed that the optimum inclusion level of cowpeas into rabbit weaner diets was 25%.

Keywords; Feed Conversion Ratio, Feed intake, Weight gains, Economics of feeding diets

Introduction

Backyard rabbit farming has recently enjoyed preference in Zimbabwean agricultural systems, Gono *et al*, (2013). This is largely due to the ability by rabbits to survive on simple feed stuffs, Lebas *et al*, (1997) The ability to utilize high roughage feed resources and the ability to thrive on simple plant products, with minimum supplementation give rabbit production a comparative advantage over other livestock enterprises, Lebas *et al*, (1997). Although current production level in Zimbabwe is not clear, there is evidence of low production due to a number of challenges, chief amongst them being feed unavailability (Gono *et al*, 2013), this results in retarded growth and subsequently low production efficiency, hence the need to come in with some intervention strategies. In Zimbabwe low production pointing to protein challenges has been cited in Mount Darwin district, Tembachako *et al*, (2017).

Whilst a lot of work to address protein challenges has been done at a global level (Matondi *et al*, 2015), in Zimbabwe use of local resources to address protein challenges in rabbit production need to be explored. Work on cowpeas by Matondi *et al*, (2015) produced positive results up to 20% inclusion level, hence the need to

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come up with an optimum inclusion level to make full use of it. Cowpea is thus a strategic crop which has the potential to address protein challenges for livestock feeding in semi-arid regions owing to its adaptation. This will improve on feed management without use of commercial feeds whilst improving on rabbit productivity for the small holder producers in the marginal rainfall areas where cowpea has better potential than soya beans, N2 Africa, (2014). Work by Matondi *et al*, (2015) indicated progressively positive results up to 20% inclusion level of cowpeas as protein source. It is therefore important to assess its performance at higher inclusion levels so as to establish the optimum inclusion level which will reduce use of the costly soya beans as conventional with no compromise on returns. Whilst the presence of anti-nutritional factors in cowpeas is well acknowledged, effects can however be reduced by pre-treatment, Ikhlas and Sirelkhatim, (2016).

Materials and Methods

Experimental Animals

Thirty-six (36) *Chinchilla gigantea* weaner rabbits, eighteen (18) females and eighteen (18) males at the age of eight (8) weeks were used in the study. The number of experimental units was guided by Ferrnandez-Carmona *et al*, 2005. The rabbits were weaned at six weeks as per the recommendations by Gerald and Robert, (1992) so as to condition them towards solid feed before the start of the feeding trial. The rabbits were also numbered at weaning for easy of identification. Prior to weaning the bunnies were administered with a vitamin-mineral stress pack (Kombvit) as per the recommendations by Lebas, (2000). The same stress pack was also administered prior to feeding of experimental diets and just before any handling operation to reduce possible shock from stress.

Animal Housing

The rabbits were housed in three (3) cages, each with twelve (12) compartments of 70cm * 60cm * 50cm. The three cages were of the same size and design placed at the same height of 0.8m above the ground. For security reasons, the cages were housed in a walled shade with two 400cm * 400cm screen gates in two opposite sides for maximum ventilation. The roof of the shade was made of corrugated iron sheets at 160cm above the top of cages.

Feed

Three (3) iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic rabbit weaner diets were formulated and compounded. The diets comprised of maize, soya bean meal (control diet), mineral supplements and graded levels of cowpeas for the diets where soya bean meal was to be partially replaced by cowpeas. The diets were as follows; 0% cowpeas (control diet), 25% cowpeas and 30% cowpeas inclusion level. No direct roughage was added into the diets since hay was fed at *adlibitum*. CBC3 variety of cowpeas was used for feed formulation. It was firstly roasted for ten (10) minutes as a way of dealing with anti-nutritional factors. Although Matondi *et al*, (2015)' s work, from which this work was born used dehulled-fermented cowpeas pre-treatment method, roasting was used in this study since it is the most common locally used method.

Feeding, Measurements and Data Collection

Routine management of rabbits was just like under the normal production system. Each rabbit was fed from its own metal feed trough. Water was supplied in a 1.5litre plastic nipple water trough per two adjacent compartments. Water was always kept available. Stress pack and other water-soluble drugs were administered through drinking water when need arises. Star grass hay was also supplied *adlibitum* as the basal diet whilst the compounded supplement feed was fed in two parts, thirty grams (30g) in the morning and the other thirty grams (30g) in the afternoon. The feed quantity was gradually increased up to a maximum of 120g per day in tandem with recommendations by Halls, (2010) , 60g in the morning and 60g in the evening. The increase was at the same rate across all the treatments so that it corresponds with intake and age requirements of the rabbits.

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Refusals were weighed and recorded each morning before introducing feed for the next day. Feed intake was thus calculated from the difference between feed administered less refusals.

The trial ran for three months with the termination period coinciding with the five months physiological maturity of the rabbits (National Department of Agriculture, 1998). Feed measurements, feed refusals and rabbits' weights were measured using an Avery digital scale throughout the experimental period. All feed intake measurements were recorded every day in the morning at 0730hrs whilst weights were taken at the same time but on a weekly basis and summed up to determine overall weight gains for the whole period. Daily feed consumption was summed up to determine weekly and subsequently whole period feed intake. Using these two measurements FCR was then calculated as ratio of total feed intake to total weight gains. Feed production costs were also computed from calculations done and these were used to come up with feed cost per kilogram weight gain and projecting gross margin per dollar variable cost for each of the three diets.

Description of Study Area

The experiment was carried out at Henderson Research Institute. It is located south of the Equator in the Southern hemisphere of Africa. The Institute lies at 17°35' latitude and 30°58' longitude. The Institute receives a Savannah type of climate. According to agro-potential zonation system, the Institute is in natural farming region IIa in Mazowe District of Mashonaland Central Province of Zimbabwe. Henderson Research Institute stretches from the 28th km peg to the 35th km peg north of capital Harare, along the Harare – Bindura highway. The institute is located at an altitude of 1,300 meters above sea level, the place is in a valley. Total annual rainfall ranges between 750 mm to 1,000 mm. The rainfall is usually received from mid-November to mid-April with mid-season droughts experienced in January. Although the place receives high rainfall amount, temperature patterns are characteristic of low rainfall potential areas with a wide temperature range. In such areas, major farming activities include production of drought resistant crops and livestock. Average temperatures range from 15°C to 22°C with lowest winter temperatures going as low as 0°C in July whilst highest temperatures can go up to 35°C in October.

Research Design

Some studies in rabbit nutrition adopted the Completely Randomised Design where sex effects are not taken into consideration (Matondi *et al*, 2015). Where sex effects are factored in, a Complete Randomised Block Design has been largely adopted. The Design for this study was guided by Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, (2012).

Thirty-six weaner rabbits (eighteen females and eighteen males) were used in an experiment involving three levels of cowpeas-based diets and the two sexes in a Completely Randomised Block Design with sex as the blocking factor. Each rabbit represented a replicate and the experimental model applied was as follows;

$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + B_j + E_{ij}$, where, Y_{ij} being the total response variable (feed intake/feed conversion ratio/weight gains/feed cost) observed, μ the overall mean for (feed intake/feed conversion ratio/weight gains/feed cost), T_i the effect of the i^{th} diet on (feed intake/feed conversion ratio/weight gains/feed cost), B_j the sex effect on (feed intake/feed conversion ratio/weight gains/feed cost), E_{ij} was the random error term on the respective response variables.

Sampling Procedure

Twelve *Chinchilla gigantea* rabbit does were mated to six *Chinchilla gigantea* bucks. The does gave birth to seventy-one bunnies of mixed sexes. From these bunnies, eighteen female grower bunnies and eighteen male grower bunnies of almost uniform weight were selected to constitute the thirty-six experimental animals for the study. The animals were balanced for weight and then randomly allocated to three treatment groups of six female and six male per treatment. Two animals of each sex from each treatment diet were then randomly allocated to each of the three cages.

Data Analysis Procedure

Feed intake, feed conversion ratio, weight gains and cost of production were the variates subjected to a one-way ANOVA in randomised blocks with sex as the blocking factor using GenStat version 14. Initial weights constituted the co-variate. Mean separation for diet effects was done using Fisher’s protected Least Significant Difference (LSD) test. All the tests were conducted at 95% confidence interval.

Results

Feed Intake

Average daily feed intake trend over the weeks showed that there was a general progressive increase in feed intake from the first week up to week four for all three treatment diets, Fig 1.0. Peak intake was reached between week six and seven after which intake started to fall, then levelled off after week ten. Week five and six coincided with tropical cyclone Idai which resulted in some shock on the rabbits as reflected by the general fall in feed intake during this period. Average daily feed intake generally ranged between 50g to 80g per day throughout the whole period of the study.

Fig 1.0: Average Daily Feed Intake Trend over the Experimental period

Average daily feed intake for the whole period was not significant across all the three treatment diets ($p > 0.05$), Table 1.0. Diet one had an average daily feed intake of 64.4g, diet two had 57.4g whilst diet three had 56.7g with a grand mean of 59.5g. Since the inception weights of the rabbits were well balanced among the treatment diets, initial weights had no effect on average daily feed intake ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1.0 Average Daily Feed Intake ANOVA Results

Parameter	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	Grand Mean	SEM	P-Value	Sign	CV%
Sample Size	12	12	12	-	-	-	-	-
Initial Average Weight	835	835.42	835.42	835	-	-	NS	-
Average Daily Feed Intake (g)	64.4	57.4	56.7	59.5	3.29	0.206	NS	19.1

SEM – Standard Error of Mean, Sign – Significance

* Significantly different, NS - Not Significant

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abc – Mean values without superscript in the same row do not differ ($p>0.05$).

Feed Conversion Ratio

The FCR in this study was defined as applied by other authors who conducted feeding experiments (Houndonougbo *et al*, 2012; Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, 2012). Other authors defined it as the quantity of feed (g) which is required by the animal to gain weight by a gram (g). Some authors like Matondi *et al*, (2015) however viewed it as the ratio of weight gains (g) per feed consumption (g).

FCR fluctuated throughout the course of the experiment, it was initially more favourable, deteriorating with time. There was a general loss of weight in week six resulting in relatively low FCR due to the effects of the shock induced by bad weather. The overall results on FCR showed that there were no significant differences in FCR across the three diets ($p>0.05$), Table 2.0. Diet one had FCR of 4.68, diet two had 4.88 whilst diet three had 5.29 with a grand mean of 4.95. Initial weights had no effect on the FCR ($p>0.05$).

Table 2.0: Feed Conversion Ratio ANOVA Results

Parameter	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	Grand Mean	SEM	P-Value	Sign	CV%
Sample Size	12	12	12	-	-	-	-	-
Initial Average Weight	835	835.42	835.42	835.28	-	-	NS	-
Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)	4.68	4.88	5.29	4.95	0.27	0.266	NS	18.7

SEM – Standard Error of Mean, Sign - Significance

* Significantly different, NS - Not Significant

abc – Mean values without superscript in the same row for diet do not differ ($p>0.05$).

Although diet had no significant effects on the conversion ratio ($p>0.05$), the FCR however indicated a deteriorating trend with the increasing level of cowpeas, hence feed conversion efficiency followed the same pattern. Diet one had conversion efficiency of 21.37%, diet two had 20.49% whilst diet three had 18.90%.

Weight Gains

Average daily gains started with relatively high gains which followed a decreasing trend with time across the three treatment diets. Results showed that the 0% cowpeas diet (diet one) was generally higher in terms of average daily gains over the whole period except form the ninth week up to the twelfth week, Fig 2.0

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Fig 2.0 Average Daily Weight Gains Trend over the Experimental Period

Weights trend over the experimental period had an inverse relationship with the weight gains trend due to the decreasing weight gains over time. The average inception weights were 835g per rabbit for 0% cowpeas diet and 835.28g per rabbit for 25% cowpeas diet and 30% cowpeas diet. Average final weights were 2003.67g per rabbit for 0% cowpeas diet, 1834g per rabbit for 25% cowpeas diet and 1777.83g per rabbit for 30% cowpeas diet (diet three). Weight trend graph shows that diet one had the highest average weight throughout the experimental period, Fig 3.0.

Fig 3.0: Weights Trend

The 30% cowpeas diet had significantly lower percentage weight gains ($p < 0.05$), Table 3.0. The percentage weight increases were 142.4, 120.2 and 113.4 for 0% cowpeas diet, 25% cowpeas diet and 30% cowpeas diet respectively with a grand average percentage increase of 125.3. Initial weight had effects on the overall percent weight gains ($p < 0.05$).

Daily average weight gains for the whole period were significantly lower for 30% cowpeas diet ($p < 0.05$), whilst the 25% and the 0% cowpeas diets were not significant, Table 3.0. The 0% cowpeas diet had daily average weight gains of 13.91 g, 25% diet had an average of 11.89g whilst 30% diet had an average of 11.22g with a grand average of 12.34g. Initial weights had no effects on daily average weight gains ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3.0: Weight Gains ANOVA Results

Parameter	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	Grand Mean	SEM	P-Value	Sign	CV%
					Diet			
Sample Size	12	12	12	-	-	-	-	-
Initial Average Weight	835	835.42	835.42	835.28	-	-	NS	-
Average Daily Weight Gains(g)	13.91 ^b	11.89 ^{ab}	11.22 ^a	12.34	0.735	0.038	*	20.6
Percent Weight Gains	142.4 ^b	120.2 ^{ab}	113.4 ^a	125.3	7.82	0.035	*	21.6

SEM – Standard Error of Mean, Sign - Significance

* Significantly different,

NS - Not Significant

abc – Mean values with the same or without superscript in the same row for diet do not differ ($p>0.05$).

Economic Performance of the Diets

The control diet had a higher cost of feed than the other two diets ($p<0.05$). The average feed costs were \$2.44, \$2.08 and \$2.04 for 0% diet, 25% diet and 30% diet respectively with a grand average cost of \$2.19. Initial weights had no effect on average feed costs. Projected average cost of a kilogram weight gain was not different across all the three diets ($p>0.05$), Table 4.0. Initial weights also had no effects on feed costs per kilogram weight gains ($p>0.05$).

Table 4.0: Economic Performance Results of the Diets

Parameter	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	Grand Mean	SEM	P-Value	Sign	CV%
Sample Size	12	12	12	-	-	-	-	-
Initial Average Weight	835	835.42	835.42	835.28	-	-	NS	-
Average Feed Cost (\$)	2.443 ^b	2.081 ^a	2.038 ^a	2.187	0.12	0.048	*	19.2
Cost per Kg Weight gains (\$)	2.11	2.11	2.27	2.16	0.12	0.561	NS	18.5

SEM – Standard Error of Mean, Sign - Significance

* Significantly different, NS - Not Significant

abc – Mean values with the same or without superscript in the same row for diet do not differ ($p>0.05$).

Results of this study showed that more time would be required to attain a kilogram weight gain as cowpeas inclusion level was increased, Fig 4.0. This meant that the rabbits would reduce their weight gains with higher cowpeas levels in the diet.

Fig 4.0: Duration and Cost per Kg Weight Gain

Discussion

Feed Intake

Initial weight did not affect feed intake since the animals were balanced for weight. The general acceptance of the new feed is attributable to enough adaptation period provided for the rabbits and use of stress pack as recommended by Lebas, (2000). This was probably the reason why feed intake was contrary to the idea by the National Department of Agriculture, (1998) that feed changes in rabbit production are associated with a drop in the initial feed intake due to feed change over shock. In this study, the rabbits readily accepted the feed across all the treatment diets. The animals had however been exposed to hay and solid feed in form of rabbit pellets during the period when they were still suckling. This could have been ample time to stimulate caecal bacterial activity thus reducing possible digestive upset as a result of dietary changes (Ministry of Agriculture and Lands, 2009). The animals also got a two-week post weaning adaptation period solely on solid feed so as to condition them before the start of the experiment. This was enough time to have them adapted so that they do not succumb to the apparent feed change-over shock from milk to rabbit pellets, then experimental diets.

The same intake pattern was also observed by other authors. In a cowpea feeding trial, Matondi *et al*, (2015) observed the same initial feed intake pattern except for the control diet whose intake was initially depressed. Although Houndonougbo *et al*, (2012) looked at feeding rabbits with Palm-Press Fibres-Based Diets they also observed a similar initial feed intake trend and this suggests that acceptance of new diets by rabbits is not a challenge if changing of feed is properly managed. With these similar observations, Muriu *et al*, (2001) attributed this uniform acceptance of new diets by rabbits to the fact that rabbits exhibit high chances of a poor sense of smell.

Feed intake trend was not in agreement with that of Matondi *et al*, (2015) who observed an increasing trend throughout the experimental period. This was possibly because the rabbits were subjected to a feeding period covering only the early stages of post-weaning growth as contrasted to a long period extending to the onset of sexual maturity of the rabbits in this study. As rabbits become mature, their caecal activity become more adapted (Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, 2012), thus they will be able to eat more hay. High intake of CF from the unlimited hay might have resulted in caecal impaction and limited intake of the feed so as to regulate energy intake (Cheeke, 1983), thus feed intake fell from the peak before it levelled off during the late post-weaning period in this study. This allows the rabbits to make full use of hay resulting in a possible reduction in intake of the feed. This is strongly supported by (Lebas *et al*, 1997) in their view on the importance of hay feeding in rabbits.

The findings from this study in terms of feed intake are however contrary to those of Matondi *et al*, (2015) whose study remained silent on sex as a block or factor. They noted significantly lower feed intake ($p < 0.05$) for one of their diets and attributed this to low protein content in that particular diet compared to the other three diets. The diets used in this study were both iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic. Feed intake results from this study strengthen the view by Matondi *et al*, (2015) that low protein level of diet two in their study might have affected intake since intake of iso-nitrogenous diets from this study did not differ. The same idea is also supported by Igwebuikwe *et al*, (2013) who attributed similar voluntary feed intake of sorghum-based diets to quality of dietary protein. The lower intake observed by Matondi *et al*, (2015) in one of the diets can also be explained from the energy content aspect as the affected diet had significantly higher energy compared to the other diets. High energy level tends to reduce feed intake as animals feed to satisfy their energy requirements (Maertens and Gidenne, 2016). The diets in this study were iso-energetic and thus feed intake was also the same.

Although they used cowpeas husks, findings by Mohammed and Jamala, (2013) were in line with those of Matondi *et al*, (2015) in terms of feed intake. The diets too had varying levels of crude protein. Daily feed intake results from their work ranged between 44.14g to 64g across the four treatment diets. Compared to the results from this study, in this study cowpeas compared better and feed intake was very close to the 60 grams recommendation, (Halls, 2010).

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Observations on Lablab based diets feed intake by Shaahu *et al*, (2014) compare very low from those of this study. Shaahu *et al*, (2014) recorded feed intake range of 15.12 to 21.76 grams per rabbit per day. This point to the fact that cowpeas could be better off as a non-conventional protein source than other legumes since its better acceptable.

In their evaluation of processed velvet beans as a non-conventional protein source, Ani and Ugwuowo, (2011) made similar observations on feed intake as noted from this study, daily feed intake was not significant. This was attributed to the fact that the diets were iso in all key nutrients with velvet beans having been processed to reduce effects of anti-nutritional factors before formulation of the feed. The poor feed intake observed from the 25% cowpeas diet during week six could have been due to poor health exhibited by one of the rabbits possibly due to impact of tropical cyclone Idai. Based on the supporting evidence from other authors and the feed intake results of this study, cowpeas, like other non-conventional protein sources, has got no adverse effects on feed intake by rabbits when incorporated as protein.

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

Week six coincided with bad weather due to cyclone Idai and this resulted in a general loss of weight. Rabbits are reported to be affected by any kind of stress, Lebas, (2000). The cold weather accompanied by a serious draft might have imposed some stress on the rabbits. Although weekly FCR fluctuated throughout the course of the trial it was initially more favourable, decreasing with time. This was in line with (Maertens and Gidenne, 2016) who noted that initial FCR is generally high due to high tissue deposition.

The numerical deterioration in FCR with increasing level of cowpeas could be probably due to the cumulative effects of the phytates and anti-trypsin factors. Although cowpeas contain less amounts of the most common anti-nutritional factors compared to soya beans (El-Shemy *et al*, 2000; Thenmozhi, 2016), it has a significant amount of anti-chymotrypsin (Ikhlas and Sirelkhatim, 2016). Whilst pre-treatment of the cowpeas helps to counter the effects of these anti-nutritional factors, in cowpeas heat treatment through pressure cooking is reported to return and fix phytates (Betancur *et al*, 2012). This might have been the case in this study, since the cowpea was heat treated through roasting. Anti-nutritional factors which react to heat treatment like phytates might have been returned and fixed, thus they could have impaired with the feed utilisation efficiency especially with higher levels of cowpeas. It must also be noted that pre-treatment does not completely eliminate anti-nutritional factors but just reduce their effects (Yacout, 2016).

Diet effect on FCRs from this study was not significant and this supports the fact that the diets were iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic. Though in the same range with those of Matondi *et al*, (2015), the significant differences noted by Matondi *et al*, (2015) might have arisen from different crude protein levels in the diets used and probably effects of no blocking for sex which the study fell short of. Just like the observations made by Matondi *et al*, (2015), this study also recorded the most favourable numerical FCR from the control diet.

The FCRs from this study were however lower than those observed by (Mohammed and Jamala, (2013) who recorded ratios from 2.97 to 4.33. Houndnougbo *et al*, (2012) recorded FCRs of 3.78 to 4.64 from the Palm-Press Fibres-Based Diets study. Ani and Ugwuowo, (2011) noted a higher trend of FCRs which ranged from 3.56 to 4.21. The relatively better FCRs recorded from their work may be attributable to the fact that their diets consisted of high-quality animal origin protein blend. These differences in FCRs could also be due to animal factors (age and genetics although this study identified sex) and not necessarily due to the feed component (Shaahu *et al*, 2014). Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, (2012) recorded less favourable FCRs of 6.58 to 8.06 when compared to those observed from this study. From the results of this study it can be concluded that FCR of cowpeas-based diets up to 30% inclusion level were within the range noted by other scientists who used other non-conventional protein sources.

Weight Gains

Average daily weight gains were generally high during the first six weeks of the experiment. This could be attributable to the high FCR reported during the early post- weaning growth phase (Maertens and Gidenne,

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2016). Generally, weekly weight gains trend for all the three diets closely followed the pattern observed by Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, (2012): Houndonougbo *et al*, (2012) in their Groundnut Forage Meal and Palm-Press Fibre-Based Diet feeding trials respectively. At the period of termination of this trial, the rabbits had attained five months of age, a period which coincided with the 4-6 months period reported to be the stage at which they attain their sexual maturity (National Department of Agriculture, (1998): Bunnyhugga, (2013) During this stage, growth rate is expected to be lower than the post weaning stage as much of the growth activity become concentrated on fat deposition and reproductive growth with less of weight gains (Maertens and Gidenne, 2016).

Low weight recorded in week six for diet two is attributable to low feed intake also recorded during the same week. The average weight gains results of this study were not in congruency with the trend observed by Matondi *et al*, (2015). In this study, diet one and two performed better than diet three. At 30% cowpeas inclusion level, significantly low weight gains were noted. Although the diets were iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic, this might have been due to the gradual decrease in the numerical FCR. The effects on FCR directly impact on growth performance since the two have a positive correlation (Maertens and Gidenne, 2016). Although crude protein level was not significantly different across the three treatment diets, the decreasing trend as shown by the numerical differences (20.29%, 21.71% and 22.48% for 0% cowpeas diet, 25% cowpeas diet and 30% cowpeas diet respectively) in the average crude protein content from proximate analysis results might also have imposed some additive effects on weight gains.

Average daily weight gains from this study were lower than those observed by Ani and Ugwuowo, (2011) and Mohammed and Jamala, (2013) who recorded average daily weight gains in the range of 16.19g to 20.11g and 16.61 to 17.84g respectively. This could be attributable to use of a blend of high quality proteins of animal origin (Bone & Fish meal and bone meal respectively) and plant origin protein. Houndonougbo *et al*, (2012) recorded daily gains of 19.65g to 23.07g and this might have been due to use of pure forms of proteins (lysine and methionine) to augment plant origin protein.

Based on the comparison between other authors and the daily average weight gain results from this study, cowpeas performance on weight gains was quite comparable to other potential non-conventional protein sources which have been explored. It is however important to observe the permissible inclusion levels so that higher levels which affect the gains are avoided. Results indicated that performance of cowpeas at 25% inclusion level is the same as for the control diet whilst anything above can be detrimental.

Economic Performance of the Diets

Feed costs per kilogram weight gain was not affected by diet despite the fact that more feed was required as level of cowpeas was increased due to a longer duration it would take for the rabbits to attain the weight. This could be because the most critical feed ingredient (protein source) was locally available at a much lower cost than soya beans. The results were not in agreement with Houndonougbo *et al*, (2012) who established that non-conventional feed resources (Palm-Press Fibres-Based Diets) become cheaper as inclusion rate was increased. Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Adeyegun, (2012) observed lower feed costs per kilogram gain from diets other than the control suggesting that the high cost of the conventional protein source used in the control diet is the main cause. From the results of this study feed conversion efficiency has a direct effect on the period it takes to attain a desired weight. This was also observed by Shaahu *et al*, (2014) who recorded better economic performance from diets which comprised of treated lablab due to high feed conversion efficiency resulting in fast growth rate and a subsequent cut on cost of production. Besides increasing cost of production, it was also observed from this study that the 30% cowpeas inclusion rate unnecessarily delayed attainment of the desired weight. In such a scenario, productivity is highly constrained especially during the post-weaning growth phase (Gono *et al*, 2013). Comparative gross margin analysis based on the three diets used in this study showed that the 25% cowpeas diet had the highest return per dollar variable cost, Table 5.0. Although the 30% diet proved to be the cheapest in terms of feed used during the trial, it turned to be uneconomic when fed targeting specific weight for

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age due to long growing time resulting in consumption of more feed as a result of compromised conversion efficiency. In such cases, cost of the other ingredients will contribute to economic loss.

From the economic analysis of this study and work by other scientists, it has been noted that use of non-conventional feed stuffs up to some level of inclusion had both economic benefits and convenience of being locally available at the same time reducing competition for the conventional feed sources.

Table 5.0: Comparative Gross Margin per \$VC

Expenditure									
Item	Diet 1(0% Cowpeas)			Diet 2 (25% Cowpeas)			Diet 3 (30% Cowpeas)		
	Unit Cost (\$)	Quantity	Value (\$)	Unit Cost (\$)	Quantity	Value (\$)	Unit Cost (\$)	Quantity	Value (\$)
Feed	45.18/100 kg	540.73kg	244.3	43.19/100kg	481.82kg	208.10	42.79/100kg	476.28	203.80
Kombvit	10	2	20	10	2	20	10	2	20
Esb3	25	1	25	25	1	25	25	1	25
Sanitizer									
Hay	5	20	100	5	20	100	5	20	100
T V C			389.3			353.10			348.8
Revenue									
Rabbits	3/kg	100	601.20	3/kg	100	550.20	3/kg	100	533.40
GM			211.9			197.10			184.6
GM/ \$VC			0.54			0.56			0.53

* Feed cost based on average cost of feed used during the study.

Assumptions

- Batch of 100 rabbits of mixed sex are produced per diet
- Cost of selling rabbits is \$4/kg live weight
- Prices are as at 31/3/2018
- No mortality
- No other bi-products are sold

Conclusion

Feed intake and FCR were not affected by cowpeas in *Chinchilla gigantea* rabbit diets up to 30% inclusion level. Cowpeas inclusion levels beyond 25% have detrimental effects on the growth performance of the rabbits. Economic performance of cowpeas-based diets in terms of cost for attaining targeted weight was not affected by the inclusion level of cowpeas, however the optimal inclusion level of cowpeas which balances weight gains and economics returns (return per dollar invested) was 25%. Initial weight had no effects on the parameters of economic importance. From the results of this study, it can be concluded that maximum weight gains should not be the only indicator of the cowpeas inclusion level to follow, a holistic approach which considers both maximum weight gains and economic returns matters for the rabbit producers. Economic analysis of this study indicated that use of non-conventional feed stuffs had both better economic returns and convenience of being locally available at the same time reducing competition for the conventional feed sources. The optimum inclusion level of cowpeas into rabbit weaners diet which balances both growth performance and cost of production was 25%.

Recommendations

Farmers can use roasted cowpeas as a non-conventional protein source at 25% inclusion level to enhance rabbit productivity and realise optimum returns. It is important to observe the permissible inclusion levels so that

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higher levels which affect growth performance are avoided. When considering use of non-conventional feed ingredients optimal inclusion levels should also be guided by the effect of anti-nutritional factors on all the parameters of economic importance (feed intake, feed conversion ratio and growth performance) together with the economic returns for the viability of the enterprise. Feeding trials should account for the effects of sex either by blocking or taking it as a factor as it may affect results whilst initial weight should be treated as a co-variate for more accurate results. There is however need for further laboratory work on cowpeas to isolate and quantify the various anti-nutritional factors from both treated and untreated cowpeas.

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